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1. Acronyms

3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	5 th Generation
5G-ACIA	5G Alliance for Connected Industries and Automation
5GC	5G Core
5GPPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
6G	6 th Generation
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOTI	Alliance for the Internet Of Things Innovation
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
AWS	Amazon Web Services
B5G	Beyond 5G
BGP	Border Gateway Protocol
CEI	Cloud-edge-IoT
CNI	Container Network Interface
CORC	Continuum ORChestrator
CPE	Customer Premise Equipment
CPPSoS	Cyber Physical Production Systems of Systems
CPS	Cyber Physical System
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSC	Communication Service Customer
CSP	Communication Service Provider
CU	Centralised Unit
DNS	Domain Name System
DU	Distributed Unit
E2E	End-to-End
ECN	Edge Compute Network
ECOMP	Enhanced Control, Orchestration, Management and Policy
ECS	Amazon Elastic Container Service
EKS	Kubernetes Service
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EUCEI	EU Cloud Edge IoT
FCAPS	Fault, Configuration, Accounting, Performance, and Security
FENS	Factory Edge Network Service
GCP	Google Cloud Platform
GDC	Google Distributed Cloud
GPS	Global Positioning System
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GSMA	GSM (Groupe Spéciale Mobile) Association
GW	Gateway
I4.0	Industry 4.0

ICC	Industrial Cloud Continuum
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IoT	Internet of Things
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
K8s	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LKC	Linux Kernel Containers
LST&P	Large Scale Trials and Pilots
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
mMTC	Massive Machine Type Communication
NF	Network Functions
NFV	Network Function Virtualisation
NG-RAN	New Generation Radio Access Network
NOP	Network OPERator
NPN	Non-Public Networks
NSaaS	Network Slicing as a Service
OCM	Open Cloud Mesh
OGC	Ori Global Cloud
ONAP	Open Network Automation Platform
OP	Operator Platform
OPC-UA	Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
OS	Operating System
OSG	Open-Source Group
OSM	Open-Source MANO
OT	Operational Technology
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAT	Radio Access Technology
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RRF	Recovery and Resilience Facility
RT	Real-Time
SA	Standalone
SBA	Service Based Architecture
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SDK	Software Development Kit
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
SDO	Standards Developing Organisations
SEP	Service Enablement Platform
SLA	Service Level Agreement

SMF	Session Management Function
SNS JU	Software Networks & Services Joint Undertaking
SSID	Service Set Identifier
TAC	Tracking Area Code
UE	User Equipment
UN	United Nations
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency Communication
US	United States
VAN	Virtual Application Network
VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Manager
VM	Virtual Machine
VNS	Virtual Network Services
VPC	Virtual Private Cloud
VPN	Virtual Private Network
WG	Working Group
XR	Extended Reality

2. Executive Summary

This document corresponds to deliverable “D2.1- *State of Art review and initial design of 6G-SMART advanced manufacturing services*” of subproject 6GSMART-S. In this deliverable we analyse the three advanced manufacturing services defined in D1.1, providing for each of them an initial design for the manufacturing service components and the 6G network enablers that need to be developed to address the use cases. Evaluation methodologies are also provided for each of the service and network enablers. Overall, for *UC-1: AI-enabled quality control*, two service enablers and three network enablers are presented. For *UC-2: High precision metrology*, three service enablers and three network enablers are presented, and for *UC-3: XR enabled remote assistance*, one service and one network enablers are presented.

This deliverable will guide the development of service and network enablers in the upcoming deliverable D2.2, as well as the network enabler developments and the integrated experimentations carried out in other 6G-SMART subprojects.

3. Introduction

6GSMART is an R&D project under the Spanish UNICO framework that investigates how 5G technology needs to evolve to address the unique needs of presented by Operational Technologies (OT).

To identify the 5G/6G technologies that can best address OT requirements, 6GSMART adopts a combined top-down and bottom-up methodology:

- Top-down approach: 6GSMART will build on three reference manufacturing use cases, which push the boundaries of current network capabilities and will allow the consortium to derive requirements for future 6G networks.
- Bottom-Up approach: 6GSMART will carry out fundamental research on networking to identify technologies that can contribute to enhance performance of OT applications.

To this end, the overall 6GSMART project is organized in 4 separate sub-projects:

- 6GSMART-S, where “S” stands for *Services*. The goal of this subproject is to design and develop the three reference 6GSMART OT use cases that will guide the development of networking technologies.
- 6GSMART-EZ, where “EZ” stands for *Extreme KPIs* and *Zero Touch Automation*. The goal of this subproject is to develop networking enablers that push forward 5G KPIs in terms of throughput, latency and localization, as well as management enablers that simplify the operations of 5G/6G networks in manufacturing environments.
- 6GSMART-ICC, where “ICC” stands for *Industrial Cloud Continuum*. The goal of this subproject is to develop cloud continuum enablers applied to manufacturing environments.
- 6GSMART-EXP, where “EXP” stands for *Experimentation*. The goal of this subproject is to develop demonstrators that bring together the services developed in 6GSMART-S with the enablers developed in 6GSMART-EZ and 6GSMART-ICC.

This document corresponds to deliverable “D2.1- *State of Art review and initial design of 6G-SMART advanced manufacturing services*” of subproject 6GSMART-S, which describes a set of manufacturing service enablers and 6G network enablers that will be developed to address the requirements posed by the three project use cases introduced in deliverable “D1.1-*Definition of 6G manufacturing use cases, and associated requirements and KPIs*”.

The three 6G-SMART use cases introduced in D1.1 are as follows:

- *UC-1: AI enabled quality control*, which brings AI-vision capabilities to two different production lines deployed in BOSCH Aranjuez. The AI-vision systems generate heavy images that need to be transmitted over the factory’s wireless network to a centralized AI-vision server that processes the received images and determines if the produced part is in defect or not.
- *UC-2: High precision metrology*, targeting the remote operation of a Coordinate Measurement Machine (CMM) over a public 5G/6G network, for which the public network needs to be provide a customized service to the industrial traffic.

- *UC-3: XR enabled remote assistance*, providing holographic communications to allow a remote expert to provide assistance to workers in the factory shopfloor, for which enhanced uplink capacities are required.

3.1. Structure of this deliverable

This deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 4 is devoted to “UC-1: AI enabled quality control” and describes two service enablers and three network enablers that will be developed to address this use case.
- Section 5 is devoted to “UC-2: High precision metrology” and describes three service enablers and three network enablers that will be developed to address this use case.
- Section 6 is devoted to “UC-3: XR enabled remote assistance” and describes one service enabler and one network enabler that will be developed to address this use case.
- Section 7 summarizes and concludes this document.

4. UC1: AI enabled quality control

We describe in this section a preliminary design of the network and application enablers that will be developed to execute this use case.

4.1. Service Requirements and KPIs

As described in D1.1, the objective of the AI-enabled quality control use case is to implement a wireless AI-enabled vision system on two production lines already deployed at BOSCH Aranjuez. These production lines manufacture two different products, which from now on we will refer to as the "*AC Interface*" product and the "*EVO Membrane*" product. The AI vision system will consist of a set of cameras deployed along the production line, which then wirelessly connect to a technical room in the factory where the servers hosting the AI vision application are located.

The requirements for this use case were identified in D1.1 and are listed here for convenience:

Functional Requirements	
UC1-FR1	The designed solution should be scalable, so that the system allows for future expansion to include all visual inspection stations in the plant.
UC1-FR2	The designed solution must operate within the existing production line's cycle time to ensure <u>no negative impact on efficiency</u> .
UC1-FR3	The designed network solution should allow us to connect production lines located on different shop floors. Fiber connectivity between shopfloors may be considered, but a wireless solution is preferable
UC1-FR4	The designed network should be isolated, because the AI vision network traffic cannot interfere with the existing plant communication lines.
Non-functional requirements	
UC1-NFR1	Service level latency should be below 100 ms, where service latency is defined as the latency between the time the image is taken in the production line and the time the image is available in the centralized server for processing.
UC1-NFR2	The AI vision system and the designed network should be designed such that a defect or no defect decision can be taken within the product cycle time. In the AC Interface the cycle time is 7 seconds. In the Evo Membrane the cycle time is 9 seconds.
UC1-NFR3	In the AC Interface the system should be able to transmit 4 images of 4.5 MB. In the EVO Membrane the system should be able to transmit at 2 images of 76MB for each cycle time.

Figure 1. UC1 requirements from D1.1

4.2. Preliminary service and network design

As described in the previous section, the key challenge for this use case is the required uplink capacity to transmit the images from the production line to the AI application sitting in the technical room within the production line cycle time. The exact uplink requirements depend on the number of pictures to be taken for each part and the cycle time, and therefore need to be analyzed independently for each production process.

4.2.1. AC Interface process

Figure 2 contains a detailed analysis of how the pictures for the AI vision process are generated in the AC Interface process, and the time budget available for image transmission and image processing by the AI application. We can see the following steps in Figure 2:

- At time $T=0$, the production cycle starts.
- At time $T=2$ seconds, the part is positioned in place to take the first picture.
- Between time $T=2$ seconds and time $T=3$ seconds, 4 pictures are taken each separated 200ms, with each picture having an approximate size of 4.5MB – 5MB.
- At time $T=3$ seconds, the 4 pictures with an aggregate size of approximately 20MB are ready for transmission.
- Given that the product cycle time is 7 seconds, and the AI vision application requires 2.5 seconds to process the images and generate a response, between $T=3$ seconds and $T=4.5$ seconds, we only have 1.5 seconds to transmit the images generated over the air.
- Thus, the overall required uplink data rate to serve this production line is $20\text{MB}/1.5\text{ seconds} = 106\text{ Mbps}$.

Note that this requirement corresponds to a single production line. If multiple production lines were deployed in the same factory shop floor, their corresponding uplink data rate requirements should be added.

Figure 2. Analysis of AC Interface production line

4.2.2. EVO membrane process

Figure 3 provides a detailed description of the image generation process for the EVO membrane production line. This production line consists of 4 different positions, where the part is processed sequentially. Among these 4 positions, the first two generate a stereoscopic image by taking 4 photos with lighting from different angles. The third is a standard image that evaluates certain defects of the part. The last position is used to evaluate the part and make the decision to place it on the belt of good parts or throw it down the chute of bad parts:

- Position 1 (CAM1): First stereoscopic image of 76 MB.
- Position 2 (CAM2): Second stereoscopic image of 76 MB.
- Position 3 (CAM3): Standard image of 1 MB.
- Position 4: Algorithm evaluation and decision-making position.

We have three different parts being processed in parallel, one in each position. Therefore, the available time to process the image generated at each position is 9 seconds. Given the description above, we can see in Figure 3 how the overall upload capacity requirement for this production line is 136 Mbps.

Figure 3. Detailed analysis for EVO membrane production line

4.2.3. Envisioned network architecture enablers

In this section we present three 6G network enablers that will be developed in 6GSMART to address this use case, namely:

- Enabler 1: Proposes a multi-RAT CPE that combines 5G and Wi-Fi to deliver enhanced uplink capacities.
- Enabler 2: Proposes to use multiple AGVs to measure available uplink capacities in the target production lines and compensate the weak coverage spots.
- Enabler 3: Complements Enabler 2, by proposing a mechanism to orchestrate tasks that need to be executed in AGVs.

4.2.3.1. Enabler 1: L2 based Wi-Fi and 5G aggregation for enhanced UL capacity

Figure 4 depicts the target network architecture to integrate wireless enabled AI vision inside the BOSCH factory. A critical point in this architecture is that cameras deployed in the production lines need to be connected at layer 2 using Virtual LANs (VLANs), i.e. need to be able to natively transport Ethernet frames. Each production line is then connected using a dedicated VLAN to a Firewall, which contains all the policies for inter-VLAN communication. Notice in Figure 4 that the AI application servers are in a separate VLAN, and bidirectional reachability is required between the AI application servers and the cameras. Another critical point in the envisioned architecture is to use a multi-RAT solution, including both Wi-Fi and 5G, to increase uplink capacity. The challenge then is to come up with a novel multi-RAT CPE that can provide end to end layer 2 services while allowing to aggregate both 5G and Wi-Fi capacity.

Figure 4. High level network architecture

Figure 5 provides a high-level design for a multi-RAT CPE, which contains the following main building blocks:

- VXLAN will be used as overlay technology to provide e2e layer two transport over a private 5G network. To this end, a virtual network function will be deployed on the edge site of the private network to terminate the VXLAN tunnels.
- To enable capacity aggregation across the WiFi and 5G networks, multi-path transport technology is required. Both Multi-Path TCP (MPTCP) and Multi-Link VPN (MLVPN) will be evaluated.

Figure 5. Envisioned design for the multi-RAT multi-path CPE and proxy to be developed in SP-3

The proposed multi-RAT CPE will be developed and evaluated in the 6GSMART-SP3 project and integrated in the BOSCH factory in Aranjuez with the AI vision application developed in this use case.

4.2.3.2. Enabler 2: AGV-based Network Quality Assessment

As detailed before, the described scenario requires to transmit several images at a regular basis. To guarantee a successful transmission, it is needed to ensure a network quality. While this is normally guaranteed by the initial set up, unintended interferences or reflections caused by temporary obstacles moving around the factory (e.g., big material boxes, forklifts) might compromise these requirements.

To mitigate these challenges, we propose deploying an ad-hoc fleet of Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) equipped with 5G/6G capabilities. These AGVs will serve a dual purpose. Firstly, they will assess the network quality at each production line, providing real-time data on network performance. This assessment will be carried out as required by each manufacturing process cycle, ensuring that network quality is maintained at optimal levels throughout the production process. In cases where the signal quality does not meet the use case requirements, the AGVs will serve a secondary function. They will be coordinated to be strategically placed at specific locations that enhance the uplink capacity of the production lines. This will ensure that the production lines' requirements are met, even in scenarios where the initial signal quality is suboptimal.

For this system to function optimally, accurate localization of the AGVs within the factory is crucial. Advanced tracking systems in the AGVs will be used for this purpose. This will ensure that the AGVs are always at the right place at the right time, maximizing the efficiency of the system, which will sometimes imply its dynamical position according to the temporary obstacles.

In addition to these measures, it would be beneficial to incorporate machine learning algorithms to predict potential sources of interference. This predictive capability, combined with the flexibility of the AGVs, could allow for proactive adjustments to the system, further enhancing its robustness against the dynamic environment of the factory floors.

4.2.3.3. Enabler 3: Orchestration and resource allocation in multi-AGV systems

To realize the vision of Enabler 2, where multiple AGVs act in a coordinated manner to deliver enhanced uplink capacity to the BOSCH production lines, centralized orchestration of tasks executed in the AGVs is required.

Combined with the cloud-native paradigm, multi-access edge computing (MEC) allows for the virtualization and disaggregation of devices, such as line controllers, thereby

enabling new and evolved use cases in the industrial domain. 6GSMART-ICC¹ proposed an on-premise edge orchestrator for the management of resources in the industrial edge, aligned with the ETSI MEC² architecture. The use of MEC architectures in industrial settings presents a number of advantages. For example, some works³ have proposed the use of MEC-based industrial control systems, where line controllers can run as MEC applications, ensuring high availability of distributed controllers. Moreover, the use of MEC services can also improve the performance of industrial use cases, such as remote-controlled multi-AGV systems, by exploiting radio network and positioning information.

In the specific case of multi-AGV systems, said AGVs usually belong to the so-called field-level segment, and present certain features that differentiate them from typical edge resources. Namely, these resources are distributed, have heterogeneous computational capabilities, and sometimes are mobile. However, the integration and management of such heterogeneous devices is not considered by the ETSI MEC architecture. Previous work in 6GSMART-ICC, however, proposed an extension of the MEC-based on-premise edge orchestrator, tailored for the management of distributed industrial resources and containerized applications, with novel, extended capabilities to support the orchestration of field-level devices such as AGVs⁴.

This section proposes the use of 6GSMART-ICC's orchestration capabilities to perform (soft) real-time scheduling and resource allocation in a multi-AGV system, considering both processing and factory delivery tasks. It is assumed that service requests arrive dynamically to the orchestrator, which performs resource allocation and application lifecycle management according to a given optimization objective, such as the minimization of the production lead time, maximization of resource utilization, or minimization of resource consumption. Figure 6 and Figure 7 illustrate the integration of the on-premise edge orchestrator in the multi-AGV use case under consideration. As showcased on Figure 7, resource (AGV) management and task allocation are performed by the on-premise edge orchestrator. Without loss of generality, it is assumed that, in scenarios with several control levels, the upper controller (e.g., the line controller) runs as a MEC application within the MEC system (namely, in the MEC host or, equivalently, in the associated on-premise edge server).

The evaluation to be performed is related to the development of the task allocation and scheduling algorithms showcased in Figure 7, for at least one, but preferably two, optimization objectives. In practice, these tasks may include localization, path planning, or motion planning. Although the task allocation algorithm is agnostic to these specific types of tasks that run on the AGVs, it does consider the amount and type of resources required by said tasks in the allocation decision.

¹ 6GSMART-ICC, "D1.1: State-of-the-art review and cloud continuum design principles." July 2023.

² ETSI. "Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC); Edge Platform Application Enablement." ETSI GS MEC 011 V1.1.1 (2021-11).

³ B. Johansson, M. Ragberger et al., "Kubernetes orchestration of high availability distributed control systems," in 2022 IEEE International Conference on Industrial Technology (ICIT), 2022, pp. 1–8.

⁴ J. Palomares, E. Coronado, E. Carmona-Cejudo, et al., "Towards Field-Level Device Orchestration in Industrial MEC Deployments," IEEE Communications Magazine (*submitted to*), 2024.

Figure 6: MEC-based on-premise edge orchestration in multi-AGV system.

Figure 7: Multi-AGV factory delivery use case using 6GSMART-ICC's on-premise edge orchestrator.

4.3. UC-1 Service components

In the following sections, the operation of the artificial vision systems that will be developed to support this use case is described.

4.3.1.1. AC-Interface

For the AC Interface, an inspection system based on artificial vision along with AI algorithms will be employed. To this end, we will use a versatile bench with multiple potential positions and a variety of lighting configurations, which facilitates the assembly/disassembly of parts and optimizes image capture as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Bench for AC-Interface

The bench integrates high-precision cameras with an IMX178 sensor and a resolution of 3088x2064 for quality inspection. These compact-sized cameras (29x29x29 mm) with interchangeable 8mm lenses can be easily connected via USB to a PLC or PC.

Figure 9: AC-Interface camera

For the AI development, two AI models will be used: a position model and a surface model, as seen in Figure 10. The position model, based on OpenCV⁵ algorithms, will be used to detect the holes of the Busbars with their centers and compute their relative positions.

Figure 10: Design of AI vision system

The surface model utilizes CNN-type neural networks (YOLO v8⁶) and performs detailed detection and classification of defects such as scratches, discolorations, and dents, ensuring a comprehensive and accurate quality inspection. The choice of YOLO as a detection tool is not based on a single determining factor. One of the main reasons is that the library developed by Ultralytics, implemented in Python and based on PyTorch, is

⁵ <https://opencv.org/>

⁶ <https://github.com/ultralytics/ultralytics>

open source, which significantly facilitates its integration and development within the project framework. Priority has been given to processing and evaluation speed, considering this aspect essential despite the potential compromises in other attributes, given the strict production line cycle times required. However, an open stance will be maintained towards evaluating results during the testing phase. Should the outcomes not meet anticipated expectations, the possibility of exploring alternatives, including G-RCNN⁷, will be considered. For the algorithm choice, it has been compared against other alternatives, as seen in Table 1.

	YOLO	G-RCNN
Speed	++	-
Accuracy	+	++
Phases	1	2
Architecture complexity	+	-

Table 1: YOLO vs G-RCNN

One of the key aspects to monitor in this project is the scale modification applied by YOLO to the images. Such transformation might not be optimal for detecting defects of small magnitude. At this stage, it is premature to determine the robustness of this approach towards small-sized defects. It's important to note that, for certain types of failures, considering the total extent of the affected surface becomes particularly relevant. The segmentation functionality offered by YOLO represents a considerable advantage for the specific use case of the project.

Regarding training, the initial plan involves using YOLO with a pre-trained network with CoCo⁸ (“Common Objects in Context, a large-scale dataset for object detection, segmentation, and captioning”), as this network can help us reduce the iterations of further training with our data set. Once it is trained with images of good parts, bad parts, and different types of errors, the data set will be updated and enriched with new failure patterns as they are detected and/or in a preventive manner, in order to increase the system's robustness.

During the preliminary phase, the team will implement 'data augmentation' techniques to generate images. This process involves creating artificial images from minor modifications applied to an existing original image. This method aids in the product development phase, where the team faces limited availability of representative samples of all defects intended to be detected through artificial intelligence. Once the assembly line is fully operational, it is planned for the network to function by collecting images and making predictions without these results being associated with or affecting the production pieces. This strategy will allow, after verifying the robustness of the vision system, to consider the transition towards an evaluation mode in which real-time results are directly linked with the corresponding pieces and their quality record.

4.3.1.2. EVO Membrane

In the EVO Membrane product, an inspection system using vision technologies and artificial intelligence will be implemented. This system utilizes three cameras arranged

⁷ <https://github.com/Jianf-Wang/GRCNN>

⁸ <https://cocodataset.org>

sequentially along the production line, capturing images of the parts which are then processed on an industrial PC at the line.

The first two cameras are designed to take four photographs with flash lighting from various angles, creating a stereoscopic image (Figure 11). This method introduces an additional dimension to the analysis, allowing for an accurate assessment of surface roughness, a critical parameter to ensure the quality of the EVO Membrane product. The third camera, located in the third position, is used to identify other types of defects using conventional artificial vision techniques, thus ensuring a comprehensive inspection.

This model is based on a virtual perfect piece generated from images of selected high-quality parts. This reference serves as the ideal standard, against which the produced parts are compared to identify deviations. When these exceed a predetermined threshold, the piece is marked as defective. This approach allows for precise and efficient defect detection, ensuring that only pieces meeting the highest quality criteria reach the market.

Figure 11: Cameras arrangement in EVO Membrane

The project requires elements capable of capturing depth in images of parts with complex geometries, which are neither flat nor easily accessible, even by adding additional cameras. To assess this depth, a stereoscopic imaging technique is employed, integrating images taken from the same position but with illumination from different angles, reconstructed into a single image from four original images.

This process is carried out using an 'autoencoder'⁹ type artificial intelligence model, which is capable of consolidating information across various configurations and parameters, allowing for the visualization of the image with depth data. Using this technique, the project's goal is to perform an initial detection of defects in parts, using the information processed by the 'autoencoder'. This method is suited to the processing speed requirements dictated by the product's cycle time on the production line, as well as to the quality of the images obtained by the vision system, which are characterized by being very heavy due to their high resolution.

⁹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Autoencoder>

The possibility of adding an additional layer of artificial intelligence (such as Yolo, G-RCNN, or alternatives available on the market) to evaluate and determine the state of the piece will also be considered. However, it has been shown that, with the first layer based on the ‘autoencoder’, it is possible to discern errors with high reliability, even without resorting to an additional AI layer.

Technical details of the neural network are restricted due to information security measures and intellectual property rights, in accordance with the policies of BOSCH CONNECTED INDUSTRY (BCI from now on), a division of BOSCH CORPORATE. Despite these restrictions, the following capabilities available in the software are highlighted:

- Selection of datasets.
- Choice of information about previously captured images.
- Choice between several preset models.
- Possibility to use new models from scratch.

However, access to hyperparameters or the modification of existing models will not be allowed.

As previously explained, the datasets used in this project differ from the common standards in artificial intelligence. For defect detection, anomalies in images considered perfect are sought, based on samples of parts without defects and varying the type of anomaly. For this purpose, a training dataset has been created solely with high-quality images, free from any defects, which will remain unchanged unless manually retrained by adding new images. In the testing phase, the goal is to work with images directly from the production line, capturing parts with and without defects to various degrees, in order to adjust the training model. The datasets for this product have already been generated and incorporated into the assembly line.

4.4. Proposed validation methodology and target KPIs

We describe in this section the envisioned validation methodology to be applied for the AI vision service, and for each of the three 6G SMART enablers that are developed for this use case.

4.4.1.1. AI vision service evaluation

Based on the defined requirements, here are suitable Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). These KPIs address the functional and non-functional requirements of the project, ensuring that the designed solution meets performance expectations:

- **Scalability:** Percentage increase in the number of visual inspection stations accommodated by the system over time. This metric ensures the system's scalability in adapting to future expansions.

- **Cycle Time Adherence:** Percentage of time the system operates within the production line's cycle time. This metric monitors the system's efficiency and ensures it does not negatively impact production line performance.
- **Network Connectivity:** Network uptime percentage for interconnecting production lines across different shop floors. This KPI ensures reliable connectivity between production lines while considering both wired (fiber) and wireless solutions.
- **Network Isolation:** Incidents of network interference between AI vision network traffic and existing plant communication lines. This metric tracks the effectiveness of network isolation measures to prevent interference.
- **Service Latency:** Average service latency in milliseconds for image processing from production line capture to centralized server availability. This KPI ensures timely processing of images, with latency below the specified threshold of 100 ms.
- **Decision Time:** Percentage of defective or no-defect decisions made within the product cycle time of 7 seconds. This metric measures the system's ability to provide real-time decisions aligned with production requirements.

4.4.1.2. Enabler 1: L2 based WiFi and 5G aggregation evaluation

The multi-RAT CPE described in section 4.2.3.1 will be evaluated following an experimental approach, consisting of three phases:

- First, the developed multi-RAT CPE will be developed and tested in the laboratory by i2CAT, using a private 5G network available at i2CAT.
- In a second phase, the multi-RAT CPE will be integrated with the NOMAD-5G solution developed by Neutron.
- In a third and final phase the integrated NOMAD-5G and multi-RAT CPE solution will be deployed in the BOSCH factory, targeting at least one of the two production lines that are part of this use case.

The main KPIs used to evaluate the WiFi/5G aggregation solution are:

- **End-to-end throughput:** Measured between the Ethernet interface of the device connecting to the Multi-WAT CPE, and the Ethernet interface of the OT device at the other side of the private 5G network connecting to the data network.
- **End-to-end delay:** Measured between the Ethernet interface of the device connecting to the Multi-WAT CPE, and the Ethernet interface of the OT device at the other side of the private 5G network connecting to the data network.

4.4.1.3. Enabler 2: AGV-based Network Quality Evaluation

The AGV-based Network Quality Assessment described in section 4.2.3.2 will be evaluated following these steps:

- First, the proposed algorithms will be evaluated analytically, to understand the performance improvement under different circumstances. Whenever needed, the algorithms will be adapted to ensure its usefulness under any circumstance.
- Secondly, the proposed solution will be evaluated in a simulator environment. For instance, the Gazebo ROS¹⁰ simulator looks like a promising tool for this evaluation.

The main KPIs used to evaluate this solution are:

- **Image Transmission Success Rate:** The percentage of images successfully transmitted without loss or corruption where the problem is only caused by obstacles in the line of sight with the Access Point. This KPI directly measures the primary function of the system.
- **Network Quality:** This could be measured using various sub-indicators such as signal strength, latency, jitter, and packet loss at each production line. A higher network quality would generally lead to more successful image transmissions.
- **AGV Deployment Efficiency:** measured by the time taken for AGVs to reach the required locations for enhancing uplink capacity. Faster deployment times would mean less disruption to the production process.
- **Localization Accuracy:** The precision with which the AGVs are able to determine their position within the factory. Higher accuracy would enable more effective deployment of AGVs.
- **Interference Prediction Accuracy:** The percentage of correctly predicted interferences by the Machine Learning algorithms and caused by the moving obstacles. Higher accuracy would allow for more proactive and effective adjustments to the system.
- **System Adjustment Time:** The time taken for the system to adjust to changes in the factory environment, such as the appearance of temporary obstacles. Faster adjustment times would mean less disruption to the production process.

4.4.1.4. Enabler 3: Multi-AGV resource allocation evaluation

The task allocation algorithm introduced in section 4.2.3.3 will be evaluated following a simulation-based approach, consisting of the following phases:

- Simulation of a dynamic multi-AGV environment, with several moving AGVs and a large number of tasks to be performed.
- Simulation of the proposed task allocation algorithm in the aforementioned simulated dynamic environment.
- Evaluation of the proposed task allocation algorithm versus a baseline solution, such as a heuristic, a random allocation process, or the Kubernetes scheduling allocation mechanism.

¹⁰ <https://classic.gazebosim.org/>

The main KPIs to be achieved are the following:

- Definition of at least one optimization objective (but ideally two). The initial optimization objective is the minimization of **process completion time**, where a process is composed of a given set of tasks. In addition, the minimization of **system energy consumption** might be considered.
- The proposed algorithm/s should outperform at least one baseline solution in terms of the optimization objective (initially, process completion time, although system energy consumption might be considered in addition).

5. UC2: High precision metrology

We describe in this section a preliminary design of the network design and application enablers that will be developed to execute this use case.

5.1. Service Requirements and KPIs

As described in D1.1, the objective of the High Precision Metrology use case is to implement 6G connectivity in a metrological infrastructure in order to provide the capacity to remotely configure and operate a CMM (Coordinate Measuring Machine). The system will consist of a set of cameras deployed in the CMM to visualize the point that is being measured in detail as well as the complete part, a sensing kit that will retrieve relevant info about the correct operation of the machine and a system to remotely control and operate the CMM in response to the data retrieved by the cameras and the sensors in response to any relevant event.

The requirements for this use case were identified in D1.1 and are listed here for convenience:

Table 2. UC2 functional and non-functional requirements

Functional Requirements	
UC2-FR1	<p>The solution shall allow the operator to control the quality control equipment remotely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The solution shall allow the operator to remotely control the movement (position and speed) of the quality control equipment's axis (and the integrated sensing tool). - The solution shall allow the operator to remotely control the configuration and operation of the sensing tool (optical laser sensor) - The solution shall allow the operator to receive the position of the sensing tool (or/and the 3D points scanned by the sensing tool)
UC2-FR2	<p>The solution shall give the operator access to real-time video captured in the quality control lab by full-HD cameras:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The solution shall allow the operator to change between full-HD and low-resolution cameras configuration. - The solution shall allow the operator to select the camera to visualize / to choose both or individual cameras visualization.
UC2-FR3	<p>The solution shall allow the monitoring of the quality control systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The solution shall give the operator access to sensors data monitoring quality control equipment systems (air pressure, energy consumption, linear and rotary axis alarm events, control lab, CMM and piece temperatures, etc.)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The solution shall allow the operator to adjust sensors data monitoring frequency.
UC2-FR4	<p>The solution shall allow the operator to prioritize traffic for each service (remote control, remote visualization and system monitoring):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The solution shall allow to establish rules to adjust the traffic priority of the services based on 4 levels (critical, severe, alarm, warning)
Non-functional requirements	
UC2-NFR1	<p>The 5G/6G network shall be stable enough to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guarantee continuous operation. - Enable safety of operation: quick reaction to alarms and events
UC2-NFR2	The 5G/6G network shall allow to prioritize traffic according to the stakeholder's criteria.
UC2-NFR3	Packets loss should be zero. Reliable transport protocols should be used.
UC2-NFR4	Latency should be under 12-14 ms for remote control of the equipment
UC2-NFR5	Transfer rate should be able to transmit Full-HD video for real-time video.
UC2-NFR6	Transfer rate shall be able to transmit video, position coordinates of a set of points, sensors measurement dataset (air pressure levels in 3 axis, electric current/power, 3 linear and 2 rotary axis positions, room, CMM and piece temperatures, ...).
UC2-NFR7	Traffic data related to the sensing tool position shall include a time-stamp to ensure data reception order is not altered.
UC2-NFR8	A switch should be used to give access to RobotLink, Sensors Hub and Remote Cameras services/modules to a 5G CPE.
UC2-NFR9	Latency lower than 4 ms for the transmission of critical data

5.2. Preliminary service and network design

When it comes to defining the architecture for the orchestration of remote high-precision metrology services, this document presents the first designs based on the preliminary analysis carried out in deliverable "D1.1- Definition of 6G manufacturing use cases, and associated requirements and KPIs". In this document, in addition to an architecture proposal for UC2, two independent locations or production domains were defined: i) the production and quality control room, where the Trimek Vulcan measuring machine and the M3 Edge are located, and ii) the control room or remote metrologist's work area.

To ensure the correct transmission of information between these two locations, a continuous flow of data will be established through the 5G/6G network. Three main data flows can be distinguished:

1. **Data from cameras** installed on the measuring machine to capture both an overall view of the movement of the machine around the part to be measured and a detailed image of the measuring tools, e.g. contact probes, and their movement around the part.
2. **Data from monitoring sensors.** These sensors periodically collect information on air pressure, air flow, and temperature - critical elements for monitoring the correct operation of the measuring machine.
3. **Remote control/positioning information** of the CMM (Coordinate Measuring Machine), via a joystick.

The direction of the flows will depend on the stakeholders' criteria, and it can be unidirectional or bidirectional. See Figure 12 for reference.

Figure 12: Data flow between domains

Innovalia Association will be responsible for adapting the communication modules, as well as developing a smart switch for the RobotLink components, the Sensor Hub and the remote camera services/modules to connect from the M3 Edge to the remote worker. Considering the types of data and their transmission flows, it is possible to prioritise between them. In this respect, the systems with the lowest requirement for low latency levels are those described below.

On the one hand, quality control systems:

- Must allow the operator to access data from sensors monitoring the quality control equipment systems (air pressure, temperature and air flow) as well as power consumption or alarm events from the linear and rotary axes.
- It should allow the operator to adjust the monitoring frequency of the sensor data.

On the other hand, the solution shall also allow the operator to access the real-time video signals captured in the quality control laboratory by 2 Full HD cameras:

- It shall allow the operator to switch between Full HD and low-resolution camera configuration.
- It shall allow the operator to select the camera to be displayed or choose to display both cameras or individual cameras.

Next, we introduce the network enablers that will be developed to support this use case, classified in: communication enablers and orchestration enablers.

5.2.1. UC2 communication enablers

The use case presents the requirement to use public networks that can provide a differentiated service to the metrology flows. Given that this is currently not possible using commercial 5G NonStandAlone (NSA) networks, to support UC2, a private 5G network will be used to emulate the performance of public 5G in a controlled environment.

The proposed design leverages and simulates the use of 5G/6G network resources available in a public network. The 5G/6G network should be sufficiently stable to ensure continuous operation and enable fail-safe operation: fast reaction to alarms and events. In addition, the transmission rate must be able to transmit the three flows under consideration: the video image, the data collected by the sensors and the data and position coordinates of the CMM controller.

5.2.1.1. Communication requirements

To manage and coordinate operationally and according to the relevance of the metrological services of UC2, the different data and information flows must meet the following requirements:

- *Prioritise channels over background traffic*

Traffic management is a crucial aspect of the 5G network as it needs to operate in real-time with ultra-low latencies, and there are various Internet of Things (IoT) devices with different bandwidth requirements that make it challenging. In the deliverable "D1.1 - Definition of 6G manufacturing use cases, and associated requirements and KPIs," it was mentioned that traffic management would be one of the key non-functional requirements of this project. For instance, in UC2, the signal related to the metrology machine control will have more stringent requirements, while the signal with camera and sensor data is less critical for the production process and is, therefore, placed in lower priority levels.

This prioritisation of channels against background traffic will be done through the use of QoS Class Identifiers (QCI) in 5G and through network segmentation or slicing. QoS tools are focused on classifying connection types by service and ranking their importance according to an order established by the operator, prioritising packets to be handled before others in the queue. As for network segmentation, it will allow network operators to create multiple virtual networks, each serving applications with individual performance characteristics.

All in all, these components will allow remote workers to perform intelligent traffic control and management, where they will be able to reduce network congestion by pausing or slowing down certain data flows to improve bandwidth for the most important traffic. The solution will allow the operator to prioritise the traffic of each service (remote control, remote visualisation and system monitoring) according to 4 levels (critical, severe, alarm, warning).

5G/6G can enable modularity and reconfigurability of the production process, providing connectivity to various elements of the use case. Considering the complexities of the production process and the layout of industrial facilities, a crucial decision must be made

as to which specific use case elements should be mobile and which should be fixed. This decision will ultimately define the architecture and layout of the 5G network components.

- *Transmit streams with low latency*

Low latency is crucial to deliver efficient cloud-based services within the Internet of Things. Critical control data in this use case must be transmitted with guaranteed latency and packet loss.

In Deliverable D1.1 it was pointed out that, while camera and sensor data are not particularly critical for the production process, remote machine control data are, and therefore in this use case they should be transmitted with latencies of less than 4 ms.

Therefore, one of the main objectives of the use case will be to work on the maximum latency reduction for this type of critical data. Considering that such low latency is not possible today, a realistic target would be 12-14 ms. In addition, it will also be necessary to transmit other non-critical, non-control-related data streams over the 5G network.

5.2.1.2. Comm. Enabler 1: 5QI/slicing based prioritization

As mentioned above, due to the particularities of the 5G/6G network it will be possible to prioritize traffic according to the criteria of the stakeholders. Reliable transport protocols should be used to avoid, as far as possible, packet loss during data transmission. It should be noted that in the case of the control module, such loss should be non-existent.

To achieve this, a QoS (Quality of Service) class identification mechanism called 5QI will be used to classify the different packets transmitted over the network into different QoS classes.

In this way, QoS can be tailored to specific requirements and each QoS class can be assigned its own characteristics (such as delay or packet loss). As a result, some packets may get better QoS than others.

Considering an architecture where Internet access services are provided through network layers in parallel to specialised services at other layers, 5QI could be used as a traffic management measure to provide Internet access services that comply with standards on reasonable traffic management oriented to the provision of different "traffic categories".

Figure 13: Network segmentation in UC2

The main features of this system include the following, as can be seen in Figure 13:

- A PDU session can carry one or several QoS flows, where all QoS flows in a given PDU session are sent through the same NG-U tunnel.
- The QoS Flow ID (QFI) is used to identify a QoS flow in a PDU session.
- User plane traffic with the same QFI within a PDU session receives the same traffic forwarding treatment, e.g. scheduling or admission threshold.
- A radio bearer can carry one or several QoS flows. Each PDU session has a unique set of radio bearers and the gNodeB decides through which radio bearer a QoS flow is sent.

Although the NOMAD-5G solution developed by Neutron to implement UC2 does not support UPF (User Plane Function) flow classification, we could emulate QoS per flow through multiple SIMs. For example, and characterising it according to UC2, the remote worker would be connected to the CPE with 2 SIMs:

- SIM1 for cameras: QCI1
- SIM2 for sensors: QCI 2

Each SIM will have a different IP address and routing will be configured to ensure that data flows through the appropriate interface.

Schematically, this network partitioning could be implemented with the following two slices, where the actual values for QCIs and RAN resource reserved ratio will be object of study during the project.

Slice = default	Slice = metrology
- SNSSAI (Single – Network Slice Selection Assistance Information) = default	- SNSSAI = metrology
- APN (Access Point Name) = internet	- APN = metrology
- RAN Reserved Resource ratio = 90%	- RAN Reserved Resource ratio = 10%
	- QCIs -> can be allocated by SIM

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - QCI = 9 (best effort) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o QCI = 3 for critical data streams from the remote worker's SIM card o QCI = 5 for data streams from cameras and sensors.
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5.2.2. UC2 orchestration enablers

In this section, we present two orchestration enablers under development in 6GSMART-ICC to address this use case.

5.2.2.1. Orch. Enabler 1: Continuum orchestrator (CORC)

UC2 components present a distributed architecture, which includes machinery, cameras, sensors, and a remote-control location, and which must be jointly managed during the production process. Thus, the cloud-continuum is a key enabler to provide a solution that satisfies the requirements of UC2. The cloud-continuum architectural model integrates resources and services across various environments, such as on-premises, edge, and public clouds. By applying cloud continuum orchestration, the IT infrastructure can be scaled up or down on demand, to match resource allocation to the needs of workloads. This elasticity eliminates the need for overprovisioning resources, optimizing costs and ensuring that the infrastructure can handle peak demands without performance bottlenecks. In this context, in UC2, cloud continuum orchestration mechanisms will allow the deployment of end-to-end applications across computing resources distributed in multiple locations of the continuum, thus enabling, for example, the deployment of remote-control components away from the production floor, and the retrieval of sensor data.

Figure 14 shows the integration of the continuum orchestrator (CORC) developed in 6GSMART-ICC over a testbed infrastructure that resembles that of UC2, to enable the deployment and management of a distributed test application for production process remote control. Said infrastructure will comprise nodes representing three different domains in the cloud continuum, namely extreme-edge, edge, and cloud. The addition of the cloud layer will enable the validation of a proof of concept simulating the addition of a cloud layer to UC2, for enhanced scalability and resource controllability. The CORC is placed on top of these resources, to manage their capacity, placement of loads, and automated scaling and monitoring.

Figure 14: CORC integration in distributed remote-control environment.

5.2.2.2. Orch. Enabler 2: On-premise edge orchestration and networking enablers

6GSMART-ICC proposed on-premise edge orchestration and networking enablers which, on the one hand, allow for a finer control over resources available at the industrial edge and field level and, on the other hand, enable the deployment of containerized, distributed applications with specific networking requirements, while abstracting away the need to perform low-level host networking configurations.

The aforementioned enablers will be evaluated in the context of UC2, through a dedicated proof of concept where 6GSMART-ICC's networking operator and single-domain on-premise edge orchestrator will be used to deploy a distributed application for the remote control of a robotic arm, which represents the CMM machine used in UC2. Figure 15 represents the integration of the on-premise edge orchestrator and networking operator with the distributed robotic arm stack, where the robotic operating system components run in a robot host node, next to the robotic arm, in the field-level segment; the remote

control components run in the on-premise edge; and the aforementioned orchestration enablers also run in the on-premise edge.

Figure 15: Integration of on-premise edge orchestration enablers in UC2 robotic arm proof of concept.

5.3. UC2 Service components

UC2 shall provide remote control capabilities, remote visual access and remote monitoring of key service indicators of metrology machines. This requires the wireless transmission of a set of data streams.

Specifically, for this use case, data will be obtained from three different data streams: cameras for operational viewing, sensors measuring key parameters and machine control and guidance. A Smart Switch will be used to give access to RobotLink, the Sensor Hub and the remote camera services/modules to the 5G CPE. A graphical illustration of the data flows through the 5G network, connecting the two production domains, is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Data flows through the 5G network

The software components running at the industrial edge (M3 edge) are three: (i) the RobotLink, (ii) the Remote Cameras, and (iii) the Sensor Hub.

Module 1: Cameras

The first flow will be composed of two fullHD 3Mbps cameras and its video latency will be 100 ms. The installed cameras will allow remote viewing of the work area, offering the ability to view in detail the point being measured, as well as the entire workpiece.

The basic communication protocol assigned for the flow of the cameras will be the Transmission Control Protocol (TCP), which will be used to control the cameras. This protocol ensures reliable transfers and has flow control mechanisms to calibrate the data rate and limit the data. It will ensure that all video frames are received and recorded in order and the risk of video loss due to packet loss will be avoided.

Module 2: Sensors

The data stream from the monitoring sensors and the corresponding Sensors Hub will allow the operator to access data from sensors that monitor both key parameters of the quality control equipment (3-axis air pressure and flow levels and CMM temperatures) and parameters related to alarm generation for the remote worker (3-axis linear and 2-axis rotary positions, such as power consumption and position warnings from linear and rotary axes, etc.).

The specifications of the monitoring sensors and the Sensors Hub will be:

- Approximately 1 sample/minute/sensor shall be sent. Each sample shall be 1500B. Each sample shall be 1500B.
- Delay not critical.
- The communication protocol will be TCP (all on the same port). The protocols for the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) will be MQTT (Message Queue Telemetry Transport) and OPC UA (Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture).

Module 3: Control

Data will be collected via coordinate measuring machines (CMMs), which are equipped with the latest technology in measuring software components and sensors. From there, a data controller will send control data to the RobotLink. This will provide information on the position coordinates of a set of points as well as control/position information from the controller on the CMM and RobotLink. In practice, this solution will allow the operator to remotely control the quality control equipment:

- It will allow the operator to remotely control the movement (position and speed) of the axis of the QC equipment (and the integrated sensing tool).
- Allow the operator to remotely control the configuration and operation of the detection tool (optical laser sensor).
- Allow the operator to receive the position of the detection tool (and/or the 3D points scanned by the detection tool).

In this data flow, information will flow bidirectionally from the two production domains (see Figure 17):

- From the remote worker to the M3Edge:
 - o Delay: 4 - 14ms (depending on the signal)
 - o CMDs (=SET/GET/DO). Low traffic.
 - o TCP communication protocol.

- From M3Edge to worker:
 - o Latency: 14ms.
 - o Subscribed data (e.g. alarms, cloud points). Asynchronous. TBD data volume
 - o TCP communication protocol.

Figure 17: Data routing from M3 to robotlink, and from the measuring machine back to M3 via the Data Assembler.

Therefore, based on the previous modules and the remote metrology service that has been designed, the following tasks will have to be undertaken:

- Adaptation of Robotlink and DataAssembler to work in remote mode.
- Development of a camera control module that allows the selection of protocols: ONVIF, direct IP connection, etc.
- Development of visualisation interfaces in M3: Cameras, sensors (including access to the data repository) and a virtual joystick.
- Adapt the communications modules (OPC-UA and MQTT) to control sensors and the connection to the Sensors Hub.
- Develop a Smart Switch for M3 Edge.

5.4. Proposed validation methodology

5.4.1. UC2 service validation methodology

The developed solution will be responsible for the transfer of data between the two UC2 locations: The place where the CMM machine is physically, and the place where the remote worker performs the remote control of the CMM machine. By doing so, the different network congestions that will be simulated to validate the solution will not be a barrier for the correct performance of the remotely controlled CMM. See Figure 18.

Figure 18: Innovalia Association action areas in the remote metrology solution

Based on the analysis of UC2 as well as the necessary modules identified, a first design of the solution has been established in a private network on which the conditions and values of a public 5G network are emulated. The private network will be implemented using the NOMAD5G system developed by Neutron. NOMAD5G will guarantee access to a 5G network for Trimek metrology machines and remote workers with an overall design of the solution as shown in Figure 18. For a correct representation of the scenario in which the solution will operate, two independent cells are established, one for the M3Edge and one for the Remote Worker, as they would have different locations and therefore connected to cells with different levels of network congestion. Within this network design, the data traffic generated by the machines and the metrology worker as well as the potential network congestion will follow the scheme shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Data flows in UC2 5G network

In the following subsections, the validation methodology that is going to be applied to the different services and modules developed for the UC2 will be described.

5.4.1.1. Module 1: Cameras

Trimek currently carries out a visual check of the regular operation of its measuring machines. This means that in order to monitor the correct alignment of the CMM and the correct trajectories associated with the measurement plan and its programming, the on-site presence of a metrologist technician is required, who is able to check the machine if necessary. There is therefore no system of visual inspection of the process beyond that which a technician can carry out in person.

This is precisely one of the main requirements and motivations for this project, since this type of inspection and monitoring of the process is essential both to guarantee the accuracy of the measurement and the safety of the process itself.

Figure 20: Need for visual control in Metrology

For this reason, as mentioned above, 2 FullHD cameras will be added, for which the following KPIs will be used depending on the quality of service (QoS).

Table 3. KPIs of the Camera module

ID	Description	Target value
1	Frequency	Refresh rate of 10 frames per second with a maximum of up to 25 frames per second.
2	Latency	Not more than 100 msec.

5.4.1.2. Module 2: Sensors

Regarding the CMM operations and the camera module, currently, there is no monitoring carried out on the movements of the arm in the respective axes of movement, as well as the temperature, and key parameters of pressure and air flow. This is because the presence of a technician on-site is required to carry out such monitoring.

However, in light of the new scenario of remote operation, and after identifying these key parameters along with other parameters that are linked to ensuring the continuity of the metrological process, the following KPIs have been established:

Table 4. KPIs of the Sensors module

ID	Description	Target value
3	Frecuency	1 time every minute and sensor 1 time every 10 sec in case of alarm (alert)

5.4.1.3. Module 3: Control

In relation to remote machine control, there is a first approach to this operational model, which allows a limited level of delocalized control by the operators, but to date this is limited to facilitating the exchange of information, such as 3D models of the parts to be measured, measurement reports and the measurement plans to be executed. However, M3workspace does not allow real-time work on the CMMs or any kind of reactive action to the CMM status during the measurement process.

Aligned with this idea of sharing relevant information but incorporating the advantages of 5G/6G networks, this project aims to incorporate a remote control module to the M3 software, which has its main result in a virtual joystick for real-time operation of the measuring machine but which uses the other two modules previously described (cameras and sensors) for its use. Likewise, this control module is articulated in response to a series of CMM operation alarms that allow adjusting both the CMM control and the frequency at which data is retrieved from the sensors.

In order to monitor the correct progress of the control module, the following KPIs have been established:

Table 5. KPIs of the Control Module

ID	Description	Target value
4	Frequency	Frequency of 30hz (positions per second). Minimum 10 Hz
5	Latency	Latency no more than 14msec.

5.4.2. UC2 network validation methodology

In addition to the KPIs that apply directly to each of the 3 modules, further monitoring indicators have been established in order to be able to fully evaluate how the proposed solution meets the needs of a remote metrology system. These indicators are detailed in the table below.

Table 6. Global Monitoring Indicators of the Solution

Network KPI

Performance and latency experienced by each application Flow d		
Service KPI		
ID	KPI	Target Value
1	Solution Timeout	M3 – < 1 minute Optical sensors and cameras < 250 mseg
2	Point Cloud Resolution	Minimum 10,000 points per second. (When working locally the minimum is 30,000 per second)
3	Sensor Continuity	(Related to communication preservation) No more than 2 communication losses in a day.
4	Communication initiation	When initiating communication (how many retries are needed to initiate a connection) < 2 attempts
Experience KPI		
5	Quality of experience	Manual positioning error (with the virtual joystick) of the machine < 0,1 mm (using the probe-type tool and the remote viewing cameras)

During the solution evaluation process, measurements of the above indicators will be performed under different interference and data channel prioritisation conditions. For example, different DL interference levels in the remote worker cell and/or in the m3 Edge cell, as well as different OCIs/AMBRs priority settings for the flows in the metrology APN.

Based on these different testing conditions and evaluation of the solution, the collection of the 5 KPIs described above will be carried out. As an example, the values that the resulting solution could offer are shown in Figure 21.

Figure 21: Examples of KPIs measurement for point clouds and CMM Cameras

5.4.3. UC2 orchestration enablers evaluation methodology

We describe in this section the envisioned validation methodology to be applied for the high precision metrology service, and for each of the 6GSMART orchestration enablers that are developed for this use case.

5.4.3.1. Continuum orchestrator (CORC) evaluation

The evaluation of the CORC described in section 5.2.2.1 will include both functional and non-functional validations, as follows:

- Functional tests will validate the following aspects:
 - Provisioning and management of resources across the continuum, including compute, storage, and network resources.
 - Handling of edge scenarios, to validate the performance and resource management capabilities in environments with varying network conditions and latency constraints.
 - Support of diverse devices and applications, to assess the system's compatibility with a range of devices, operating systems, and application workloads.
- Non-functional tests will include the following:
 - Performance testing in terms of system responsiveness, throughput, and latency, under various load conditions.
 - Scalability testing, to assess the system's ability to scale up and down its resource allocation efficiently in response to changing workload demands.

- Reliability testing, to evaluate the system's resilience against failures, including hardware failures, software failures, and network disruptions.
- Security testing, including vulnerability scans, penetration testing, and security audits.

The main KPIs used to evaluate the performance of the CORC are:

- **Resource utilization:** these KPIs measure how efficiently cloud resources are being used, in terms of infrastructure, CPU utilization, memory utilization, and storage utilization.
- **Infrastructure performance:** refers to KPIs about the effectiveness and efficiency of the infrastructure for supporting the required business operations. Specific metrics include device detection time, and provisioning time.
- **Service availability:** these KPIs measure the availability of cloud services to users. Examples include uptime, downtime, and mean time to restore.
- **Service performance:** these KPIs measure the performance of cloud services in terms of speed, response time, and throughput. Examples include latency, jitter, and packet loss.

CORC will provide integrated built-in dashboards that display these KPIs in real time, allowing to monitor the performance of cloud service orchestration operations and identify potential problems early on.

5.4.3.2. On-premise edge orchestration and networking enablers evaluation

The evaluation of the on-premise edge orchestration and networking enablers described in section 5.2.2.2 will include both functional and non-functional validations, as follows:

- Functional tests will validate the following aspects:
 - Deployment of distributed robotic arm application (including operating system and remote-control elements) over a distributed architecture composed by two segments.
 - Support of specific network configurations at the host level.
 - Support of specific network configurations at the container level.
- Non-functional tests will include the following:
 - Performance testing in terms of system responsiveness and lag.

The main KPIs used to evaluate the performance of the on-premise edge orchestration and networking enablers are:

- **Infrastructure performance:** refers to KPIs about the effectiveness and efficiency of the infrastructure for supporting the required operations. Specific metrics include application provisioning time.
- **Service availability:** these KPIs measure the availability of services. Examples include downtime.
- **Service performance:** these KPIs measure the performance of services in terms of response time and throughput. Examples include latency or lag and packet loss.

6. UC3: XR enabled remote assistance

6.1. Service Requirements and KPIs

In D1.1 we introduce the XR remote assistance use case, which leverages holo-portation technology to allow real-time remote assistance in manufacturing environments.

Table 6-1 describes the requirements for this use case detailed in D1.1. Of particular importance is the data rate requirements associated with this service because each volumetric video stream may require up to 50Mbps, both in Uplink (for capture) and in Downlink (for rendering). Thus, a holoportation call with N users, would require an Uplink data rate of 50Mbps and a Downlink data rate of (N-1)*50Mbps, which can easily saturate existing public mobile networks.

Table 6-1. Functional and non-functional requirements for the XR enabled remote assistance use case

Code	Requirement		
UC3-FR1	The solution shall enable a volumetric (i.e. 3D) holographic representation of remotely located users		
UC3-FR2	The solution shall support real-time audiovisual communications		
UC3-FR3	The solution shall be easy to integrate within a shared Virtual Reality (VR) environment		
UC3-FR4	The solution shall support multiuser interaction / collaboration features		
UC3-FR5	The solution shall provide support for VR mode (i.e. usage of a VR headset for media presentation) and non-VR mode (i.e. usage of 2D screens for media presentation)		
UC3-FR6	The solution shall enable edge based VNF if the deployment is performed on a private network		
Non-functional requirements			
Code	Component	Uplink/ Downlink	Requirement
UC3-NFR1	Client	Uplink/ Downlink	The holoconferencing platform shall support at least 2 remote tele-ported users
UC3-NFR2	Network	Uplink/ Downlink	The end-to-end delays for audiovisual communications shall be $\leq 200\text{ms}$
UC3-NFR3	Client	Uplink/ Downlink	The virtual shared environment shall support at least 3 interaction modalities
UC3-NFR4	Network	Uplink/ Downlink	The virtual shared environment shall provide interactions with delay, and thus sync error, $\leq 100\text{ms}$ for event/interaction

UC3-NFR5	Capturing System	Uplink	The holoconferencing platform shall enable volumetric video streams with frame rate ≥ 15 fps
UC3-NFR6	Capturing System	Uplink	The holoconferencing platform shall enable volumetric video streams with resolution $\geq 100K$ voxels/frame
UC3-NFR7	Compression System	Uplink	The holoconferencing platform shall enable volumetric video streams with bandwidth < 50 Mbps / user

6.2. Preliminary service and network design

The key technology identified in D1.1 to address the requirements of this use case is Adaptive Traffic Steering, Switching and Splitting (ATSSS) defined by 3GPP¹¹. Using ATSSS, a Mobile Network Operator (MNO) would be able to aggregate the capacity provided by Wi-Fi inside the factory, where the two endpoints of the holo-portation call are located, with the capacity available in the public mobile network.

To deploy an ATSSS system, several components are required, which are illustrated in Figure 22:

- An XR client and XR Application Function (XR AF), exchange XR bursts, which are segmented into IP packets, before reaching the 5G/WiFi CPE, or the MNO network. Note that in a real setup, end-user devices would have embedded 5G and Wi-Fi interfaces and ATSSS capabilities, thus the CPE would not be required.
- An ATSSS User Plane (UP) function, both in the CPE and in the network side, is the key element that injects the IP packets coming from the XR client or the XR AF and distributed these IP packets through the Wi-Fi and public 5G networks. It is through this distribution of IP packets across the two networks that the effective capacity perceived by the XR application can be increased.
- To be able to aggregate both Wi-Fi and 5G IP flows on the network side, both networks need to terminate on the MNO's core. A 3GPP-compliant integration required the use of a Non3GPP Interworking Function (N3IWF), as described in D1.1. However, a non-3GPP compliant implementation is also possible where the ATSSS UP function is located behind the 5G Core, as described in Figure 22.

The main component to be investigated in this use case is the logic that can be used to balance XR traffic among the 5G and the Wi-Fi networks. R16 defines four steering modes for ATSSS, which include *active-standby*, where only one access (the active) is used until it fails, *smallest delay*, where delay is measured through each access and the smallest is used, *static load balancing*, where a fixed portion of traffic is sent through each access, and *priority-based*, where traffic is sent through the highest priority access unless congestion is detected. R17 introduced a new ATSSS steering mode known as *autonomous steering* where UE and UPF can decide autonomously how to split the traffic

¹¹ Cogalan, Tezcan, et al. "Enhanced Access Traffic Steering Splitting Switching with Utility-Based Decisioning." 2022 IEEE Conference on Standards for Communications and Networking (CSCN). IEEE, 2022.

based on an implementation-dependent algorithm. The autonomous steering model will be the basis for the investigations carried out in the use case.

Looking at Figure 22 we can see how *holo user #1* receives in downlink two holograms, each corresponding to *holo user #2* and *holo user #3*. In general, in an N-party holographic call, each user will receive N-1 holograms in downlink and will transmit 1 hologram in uplink, if using a communication architecture based on the use of Selective Forwarding Units (SFU). Each hologram may have a different encoding, and therefore different data rate requirements. In 6GSMART, we envision a new type of network API, whereby the XR Application Function (XR AF) can communicate with the ATSSS control plane (ATSSS-CP) to communicate the 5-tuple identifying each flow directed towards a given client, as well as the data rate requirements of that flow (c.f. Figure 22). Armed with this information the ATSSS-CP function can program the ATSSS User Plane (UP) function to balance the holograms that need to be received by each end user across the Wi-Fi and 5G networks. Notice that the ATSSS function may collect performance measurements from both the Wi-Fi and the 5G networks, and thus it is in the best position to take flow allocation decisions that optimize the utilization of the network.

The main challenges that need to be researched to address this use case are:

- XR application design such that different holograms directed to the same end user can be packaged in separate TCP flows, and the data rate requirements of each flow can be measured. Other XR design decisions that lead to multiple TCP flows with explicit data rate requirements can also be explored.
- The design of the ATSSS CP function, which must measure the capacity available in each network, and then based on the information provided by the XR AF, must take a network allocation decision for each flow.

Figure 22. Initial design of 6GSMART ATSSS system

6.3. UC3 Service components

Figure 22 sketches the main XR AFs that intervene in a multi-user holographic communication session, which are briefly explained next:

- **XR UP AF (UL):** It is a volumetric video capturing sub-system integrated in every client, which may be comprised of 1 to N capturing sensors. Regardless of the number of sensors, a TCP websocket stream ($IP_{source}^{client_n}$, $port_{source}^{client_n}$, $protocol$), carrying out the captured and reconstructed human body (hologram) is sent over the network, via another bi-directional in-cloud XR AF UP (i.e. an SFU), to reach the target clients.
- **XR UP AF (DL):** It is a simplified representation of the software components in charge of receiving the volumetric video streams (i.e., holograms) from all clients, decoding them, and presenting them based on some scene representation information. Media presentation can happen on an XR headset or on 2D screens. As introduced before, in SFU mode, each n -th client receives $N-1$ volumetric video streams in downlink for a session with N users.
- **XR UP AF (Bi-Directional):** It is a virtualized Selective Forwarding Unit (SFU), i.e., VNF, which is in charge of managing the exchange of volumetric video – and audio – streams from origin to destination clients via TCP websocket connections, as illustrated in Figure 22. Note that being a VNF, it can be dynamically instantiated over the cloud continuum (e.g., Cloud, Edge) if Orchestration capabilities are available.
- **XR CP AF (Bi-Directional):** It is a Control Plane (CP) AF used for managing media sessions, called *XR Orchestrator*. It also interfaces client and in-cloud XR UP AFs to e.g. request media rate adjustments.

More detailed documentation about the end-to-end HoloMIT architecture and its components is provided in¹².

In 6G-SMART, novel extensions to HoloMIT are proposed to leverage and integrate the ATSSS enablers introduced in Section 6.2. In particular, the goal consists of being able to split the delivery of $N-1$ TCP streams from the SFU to the UEs in downlink, which can become a bottleneck especially if multiple UEs in the same cell are participating in holoconferencing sessions (c.f. Figure 23). For such a purpose, a new module will be implemented to allow the XR Orchestrator (i.e., XR CP AF) to communicate to the ATSSS CP function the set of 6 -tuples (IP_{source} , $port_{source}$, $IP_{destination}$, $port_{destination}$, $protocol$, $data_rate$) describing the outgoing streams from the SFU (i.e., XR UP AF), for each source client, to a particular destination client (i.e. holo user). The transport protocol (in this case TCP, although it could be implicit) and the data rate requirements / characteristics for each stream are also indicated in such 6 -tuples.

¹² S. Fernández, M. Montagud, G. Cernigliaro, D. Rincón, "Multiparty Holomeetings: Toward a New Era of Low-Cost Volumetric Holographic Meetings in Virtual Reality," in IEEE Access, vol. 10, pp. 81856-81876, 2022

Such *6-tuples* are identified and retrieved by combining functionalities of the XR Orchestrator (i.e., XR CP AF) and the SFU (i.e., XR UP AF), and an API REST is being defined to inform the ATSSS CP function about the active streams, whenever relevant (e.g., session starts, new clients join/leave the session, etc.).

Note that the envisioned ATSSS features could also be applied to other scenarios within the XR holoconferencing domain. Examples include: (i) splitting each set of N-1 streams that the SFU sends to every client / user participating in a multi-user session; (ii) splitting the different streams (e.g., audio and video, or video captured from different sensors to reconstruct a 3D volume) exchanged between clients via the in-cloud XR UP AFs. These other applicability scenarios are out-of-scope of 6G-SMART but become a proof of relevance of the envisioned and devised 6G enablers.

Figure 23. High-level communication architecture for XR holoconferencing sessions

6.4. Proposed validation methodology

The enabler will be evaluated by means of laboratory-based experimentation. A private 5G network, including both WiFi and 5G capabilities will be provided by i2CAT. In addition, a real XR holographic application based on i2CAT's Holomit technology¹³ will be considered. Tentative experiment setups will recreate the 3-party call topology defined in Figure 22.

The following table identifies the target KPIs that will be measured in this work.

Table 6-2. UC3 related KPIs

KPI name	KPI description	Target Value

¹³ <https://i2cat.net/holoportation-technology/>

Throughput	Bits per second in uplink and downlink measured between XR AFs described in Figure 22.	<p>Depends on underlying network configurations.</p> <p>This KPI will also be measured under different signal conditions, with respect to both the WiFi AP and the 5G base station.</p>
Round Trip Latency	Round trip latency measured using standard network diagnostic tools such as ping or lagscope ¹⁴	<p>This KPI will be tested under the same network conditions defined for the throughput KPI.</p> <p>Target is to keep the round trip latency below 20ms.</p>
End-to-end latency	Capture to Rendering latency between any origin and destination holo user	<p>This KPI will be tested under the same network conditions defined for the throughput KPI.</p> <p>Target is to keep the end-to-end latency below 150ms.</p>
Reconstructed fps	Frames per second (fps) for the incoming volumetric video streams	<p>This KPI will be tested under the same network conditions defined for the throughput KPI. With network congestion, the fps values could fluctuate and be negatively impacted.</p> <p>Target is to keep the reconstruction / rendered fps as close as possible to the captured fps.</p>
Number of concurrently supported Holomit users	Number of users that can be connected to the same Holomit call	<p>The number of concurrent users will depend on the capture resolution used in the holographic system.</p> <p>We target a minimum of 10 concurrent users in a holographic call using a minimum codec rate of 6 Mbps.</p>

¹⁴ <https://github.com/microsoft/lagscope>

7. Conclusions

This deliverable presents an initial design for the advanced manufacturing services and the corresponding 6G network enablers that will be developed to address the 3 use cases considered in 6G-SMART, namely UC-1: AI enabled quality control, UC-2: High precision metrology, and UC-3 XR-enabled remote assistance.

The following table summarizes the planned service and network enablers, indicating for each enabler the 6G-SMART subproject where it will be developed.

UC-1: AI-enabled quality control	
Service Enablers	Network enablers
YOLO based vision algorithms for quality control in AC-interface process - Subproject: 6GSMART-S	L2 based Wi-Fi and 5G aggregation for enhanced UL capacity - Subproject: 6GSMART-EZ
Autoencoder-based detection algorithms for quality control in EVO-Membrane process - Subproject: 6GSMART-S	AGV-based Network Quality Assessment - Subproject: 6GSMART-S
	Orchestration and resource allocation in multi-AGV systems - Subproject: 6GSMART-ICC
UC-2: High precision metrology	
Service Enablers	Network enablers
Camera module - Subproject: 6GSMART-S	5QI/slicing based prioritization - Subproject: 6GSMART-S
Sensor module - Subproject: 6GSMART-S	Continuum orchestrator (CORC) - Subproject: 6GSMART-ICC
Robotic control module - Subproject: 6GSMART-S	On-premise edge orchestration and networking enablers - Subproject: 6GSMART-ICC
UC-3: XR enabled remote assistance	
Service Enablers	Network enablers
Holomit NaaS extension for multi-flow support - Subproject: 6GSMART-S	ATSSS for Wi-Fi-5G aggregation - Subproject: 6GSMART-S